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Article

Volunteer-led emergency flood response in Bangladesh: Evidence for strengthening disaster-risk governance

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ABSTRACT

Bangladesh is highly vulnerable to floods, like natural disasters. However, contributions of volunteer-led non-profit organizations (NVOs) in emergency response remain underexplored. This paper investigates how an NVO responded to a flood, from rapid rescue to post-flood recovery, and evaluates the effects of its engagement on public health, organizational learning and growth, and community resilience. We applied a mixed-methods approach, combining organizational document reviews, structured interviews with seven key volunteers, direct field observations, and photographic documentation of relief and medical camp activities (21–28 August 2024). Quantitative data on reported illnesses were analyzed using STATA-18 and R through descriptive statistics, univariate analysis, post-hoc comparisons, and multinomial logistic regression. Qualitative data underwent thematic analysis with a deductive coding framework. The NVO provided critical support through rapid rescue, targeted relief, and medical camps addressing integumentary (46.5%), respiratory (13.2%), skeletal (5%), gastrointestinal (2.6%), and other illnesses (32.7%). Thematic analysis highlighted organizational strengths, including field-level experience, decentralized leadership, adaptability, and strong collaborative capacity with government and other non-government actors. Despite resource constraints, the NVO demonstrated high operational effectiveness and recognition during the crisis. Formal integration of NVOs into national disaster coordination mechanisms is recommended. Institutional, technical, and financial support can strengthen disaster risk reduction, governance, and social development in resource-constrained settings. This study establishes novelty by linking health impact assessment with organizational learning in volunteer-led disaster response, combining quantitative outcomes and qualitative insights to show how grassroots organizations complement formal disaster management and provide actionable recommendations for integration into governance.

KEYWORDS

Bangladesh, community resilience, disaster response, flood, public health, volunteer-led emergency response.

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1. Introduction

Flooding is the most frequent and damaging natural disaster globally, accounting for almost half of all disaster events in recent decades and imposing disproportionate health and economic burdens in Asia (UNDRR, 2024). Between 1990 and 2020, disaster frequency increased by nearly 10%, with floods responsible for substantial rises in mortality and direct losses (UNDRR, 2024). More than 75% of people affected by natural disasters live in Asia, where Southeast and South Asian countries face recurrent hazards including floods, cyclones, and disease outbreaks (UN, 2016; WHO, 2022).

1.1. Flood in Bangladesh

Bangladesh is among the most flood-prone countries in Asia, due to its deltaic geography, with over 80% of its territory in floodplains intersected by the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna river basins (Uddin & Matin, 2021). Seasonal floods replenish soil fertility through silt deposition, but their adverse impacts have intensified under climate change, upstream water management, and governance challenges (Uddin & Matin, 2021; Partha, 2024; Barua et al., 2025). Each year, one-fifth to one-third of the country is inundated, displacing millions and disrupting health services, agriculture, and livelihoods (Rahman & Salehin, 2013; Kabir & Hossen, 2019; Hossain et al., 2020).

The August 2024 regional floods were among the worst in Bangladesh's recent history, affecting 5.8 million individuals, including over 2 million children (Muñoz & English, 2024; WHO, 2024). Triggered by monsoon rains compounded by transboundary dam "Dumbur Dam" releases, the flood inundated 11 eastern districts, destroying crops, fisheries, and homes, while displacing over 500,000 people into temporary shelters (Partha, 2024; Barua et al., 2025; Das et al., 2025). Feni district experienced particularly severe impacts due to limited early warning, with economic losses estimated at over USD 500 million (Dhaka Tribune, 2024; Sujoy, 2024). Although popularly known as the "Feni Flood," the disaster also caused devastating damage in the Cumilla, Noakhali, and Lakshmi-pur districts (Barua et al., 2025).

1.2. Sociopolitical context and volunteer response

The flood unfolded during a period of political transition following the July 2024 student-led revolution (Ahsan et al., 2025). In its aftermath, youth mobilization became a defining feature of the emergency response (Mizan & Rahman, 2024). Several non-profit voluntary organizations, including the Bangladesh Bondhu Foundation, Bangladesh Red Crescent youth volunteers, and Launch Good, played key roles in the disaster response through rescue missions, relief distribution, and medical support (Bondhu, 2024; GreenTime, 2024; IFRC, 2024; Rouf, 2024). Volunteering involves the voluntary contribution of one's time, skills, and resources to positively impact the well-being of individuals and communities (Mnisi, 2024). It encompasses activities carried out within organized structures as well as independent efforts that aim to strengthen community resilience and enhance environmental and social conditions (Mnisi, 2024).

Nogorful is such a Chattogram-based local voluntary organization (NVO), originally founded to support street children's education and wellbeing, that played an active role in both immediate rescue and post-flood recovery (Somokal, 2024; Sarowar, 2024). The NVO, operating seven informal education centers and serving over 1,000 disadvantaged children, leveraged its community trust and volunteer base of 400 to mobilize a multi-phase response (Figure 1). This longstanding community engagement positioned the organization to respond effectively during the August 2024 flood, despite limited prior experience.

Bangladesh, being highly prone to natural disasters, has been the subject of numerous studies on emergency responses to floods and cyclones (Cash et al., 2013; Rahman et al., 2017; Baten et al., 2018; Hossain, 2020). These Bangladeshi studies demonstrated how government and civil society mobilized the early warning and response phases of a natural disaster to achieve successful public

health outcomes through a multi-stakeholder, integrated approach, along with community involvement. However, the role of NVOs in such emergency response efforts has received limited scholarly attention. At the same time, our study will discuss the activities of such NVO during the response phase of a natural disaster, such as a flood. Understanding how such organizations function during disasters is essential, as their flexibility and proximity to affected populations complement formal governance structures and can inform more inclusive disaster risk governance (DRG). According to the International Committee of the Red Cross, disaster risk governance is a set of laws, policies, plans, and institutional arrangements about disaster risk management (DRM). It is a strong foundation for a DRM system capable of managing disaster risk (IFRC, 2019).

Figure 1. A map showing the distribution of the school branches of Nogorful in Chattogram division

Therefore, NVO is an important element to make effective government action during a disaster through national strategies, legal frameworks, multi-stakeholder coordination, financing mechanisms, and adaptation to climate change (IFRC, 2019). Bangladesh experienced the worst dengue outbreak after the monsoon flood in 2019 (Anon, 2022). Besides, natural disasters like floods cause mental health issues and prevent general people from getting back to their normal lives (Anon, 2022). In these situations, volunteer-led NVO activities with prior experience working with marginalized people expand emergency service coverage, including medical care, where formal response capacity is constrained (Daddoust et al., 2021; Rawat et al., 2023). Their broader service coverage improves timely access to care and support, thereby mitigating health risks and reducing disaster-related morbidity (UNDRR, 2022; WHO, 2024). At the same time, this voluntary work helps NVO members gain operational experience through response activities, thereby strengthening organisational learning, adaptive capacity, and long-term resilience (Sinha & Ola, 2021; Evenseth et al., 2022). This study aimed to explore the role of an NVO in a community and its impact on the organization's growth, including volunteers' capacity.

We, therefore, designed this study to address the following research questions:

1. How can a volunteer-led non-profit organization respond during a natural calamity like a flood, from the emergency phases through to recovery?
2. To what extent does the emergency medical support provided by a volunteer-led non-profit organization address the health risks of flood-affected populations?
3. What is the impact of a volunteer-led non-profit organization's engagement on community resilience and social development?

2. Materials and methodology

2.1. Study design

A convergent mixed-methods approach (Gibson, 2016; Fetters & Molina-Azorin, 2019) was employed to explore the activities and community engagement of the non-profit voluntary organization (NVO) during the August 2024 flood and to assess the flood-related human illnesses in its aftermath. This design was chosen to integrate qualitative and quantitative data, enabling the triangulation of multiple sources and facilitating an in-depth, contextual understanding of the organizational transformation across different phases of disaster response. The full timeline of the NVO's activities is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Timeline of the NVO's activities.

Phase	Time frame	Activities
Preparation phase	21 August, 2024	Meeting with other collaborative non-profit voluntary organizations and preparation for field work
Phase I: Immediate flood response	22-23 August, 2024	Rescue activities
	22-27 August, 2024	Relief distribution activities
Phase II: Post-flood recovery and community health response	6 September, 2024	First medical camp and relief distribution after the flood
	6-8 September, 2024	Relief distribution
	28 September, 2024	Second medical camp and relief distribution
Quantitative data	Basic clinical signs recorded on 6 and 28 September 2024 from the medical camp	
Qualitative data	Interviews were conducted in October 2024, and the transcript writing process was conducted simultaneously, taking 2 months (October and November) to complete.	

2.2. Study area and duration

NVO's immediate response and early recovery activities were conducted from 21 August to 28 September 2024, across four districts: Feni, Cumilla, Noakhali, and Chattogram (two upazilas (sub-districts): Mirsharai and Fatikchhari). During the flood, the organization coordinated rescue operations and distributed emergency relief items along with other local NVOs. In the post-flood phase, partially and fully displaced households in Feni received financial support. Two medical camps were organized in underserved upazilas, Chagalnaya (Feni) and Begumganj (Noakhali), hosted in selected schools to provide medical services to communities that had not yet received support. The locations of these activities are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. A map showing the flooded areas during August 2024 in Bangladesh, including the spots where Nogorful performed their voluntary activities.

2.3. Data collection

Data were collected through a combination of organizational document reviews, structured interviews with seven key volunteers, 800 patient data (clinical history and on-the-spot disease records), direct field observations, and photographic documentation of relief and medical camp activities. Organizations' documents included event plans, logistics schedules, volunteer task assignments, and summary reports. Publicly available materials, including news articles and social media updates (LinkedIn, Facebook, and X), were also reviewed to supplement official records. Field observations captured volunteer activities during rescue operations, relief distribution, and medical camp, providing contextual insights into teamwork, community interactions, and logistical workflows.

Structured interviews focused on: (a) volunteers' roles in the organizational growth, (b) individual and collective learning during the response, and (c) perceptions of community recognition following the activities. Medical camp data were collected through on-site registration forms to assess the post-flood health impacts among the affected population.

2.4. Quantitative data analysis

Quantitative data from medical camps were managed in Microsoft Excel, cleaned, coded, and recoded, then imported into STATA-18 and R version 4.5.1 for analysis. Only individuals (682 cases among 800 cases) presenting with illnesses were included in the data analysis; the remaining cases involving wound dressing, suturing, or relief receiver were excluded. Summary statistics were computed and expressed in frequencies and percentages. Univariate analyses of demographic characteristics (location, gender, and age group) for each reported illness were assessed using the Chi-square test, given the categorical nature of the variables and the large sample size. We examined expected

cell frequencies in which fewer than 20% of the cells were fewer than 5, satisfying the chi-square test's assumptions. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Where overall associations were statistically significant, post-hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted using standardized residuals with a threshold of ± 2.00 and adjusted p-values.

To adjust for potential confounding and assess multivariable associations between demographic characteristics (predictor or independent variables) and illness categories (outcome or dependent variables), a multinomial logistic regression (MLR) model was conducted. Model adequacy was determined using goodness-of-fit statistics, and overall model significance was evaluated using a likelihood ratio test (p value < 0.05). Given the complex nature of health outcomes in flood-affected settings, where patients' socioeconomic status, environmental exposure, and access to health services can influence disease patterns. The MLR was applied primarily as an explanatory model for this dataset rather than for prediction, which is common in public health and disaster research (Umaña-Hermosilla et al., 2020; Bezie et al., 2024). The dependent (outcome) variable, illness categorized by physiological system (integumentary, respiratory, integumentary and other, integumentary and respiratory, respiratory and other, gastrointestinal, skeletal, miscellaneous), with integumentary illness as the base outcome (reference category). The cases were classified into physiological-system categories based on clinical assessment, including presenting symptoms and findings from basic examinations such as blood pressure measurement, stethoscope auscultation, body temperature assessment, and general physical check-up. The chronic metabolic and malnutrition-related diseases were considered as the miscellaneous cases, such as diabetes, high blood pressure, weakness, and nerve pain. The cases were complex, with the main physiological diseases (integumentary, respiratory, gastrointestinal, and skeletal) and miscellaneous diseases, which were defined as other cases, for example, integumentary diseases + diabetes. Independent variables included location, gender, and age group, and were coded as numbers, for example, male=1, female=2. Results were reported as relative risk ratios with 95% confidence intervals and adjusted p-values (<0.05).

2.5. Qualitative data analysis

Qualitative data were thematically analyzed in a deductive coding approach (Braun & Clarke, 2022) by reviewing the structured transcripts. A deductive coding approach was used to identify recurring patterns and key phrases, producing the final theme across the volunteers' responses. Analysis was focused on three key domains: (a) volunteers' contributions to the organization's growth, (b) perceived community recognition of the organization, and (c) personal and organizational learning gained through participation in the disaster response.

2.6. Data triangulation

The analysis employed data triangulation by integrating both qualitative and quantitative findings to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the organization's activities and impact during the disaster response. Quantitative data on disease prevalence were measured following the flood. In contrast, qualitative data, including interviews, field notes, and photographic evidence, captured the sequence and nature of field activities, highlighting volunteer engagement, rescue operations, logistical coordination, and medical support. By comparing and corroborating findings across these sources, the study assessed the capacity of the NVOs during emergencies, demonstrated their critical role in the national disaster framework, and illustrated the personal and organizational benefits gained through participation.

2.7. Ethical considerations

Permission to access internal documents and use photographs for academic purposes was obtained from the authorities of a non-profit voluntary organization. Verbal consent was obtained from all volunteers prior to interviews, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the study.

3. Results

3.1. The organization's response to the August 2024 Flood

The voluntary support from Ngorful during the August 2024 flood was its first experience in responding to a natural disaster. On the night of 21 August, following the escalating crisis, the council of collective social organizations convened an emergency meeting with the representatives from various non-profit voluntary organizations (NVOs) in Chattogram to coordinate relief efforts for the flood-affected people. Ngorful emerged as the lead for this coordinated initiative. In collaboration with other organizations, they structured their activities into two phases of flood: immediate flood response and post-flood recovery.

3.2. Phase I: Immediate flood response

More than 200 volunteers of the organization were assigned to specific operational roles (Figure 3-5). One team of fifteen members was immediately designated for rescue operations, hiring one boat and conducting rescues over two consecutive days. Approximately 300 people were rescued. Another group of hundred-plus volunteers was engaged in raising funds through public donation booths. A separate logistics team of more than 150 members was organized to manage the procurement, packaging, and distribution of emergency relief items. The supplies included dry food, hygiene kits, candles, gas lighters, oral rehydration salts (ORS), basic pain relievers, and water purification tablets. More than 3000 people received relief through this initiative. Relief distribution activities were carried out between 22 and 27 August 2024 across the affected areas. Many individuals extended a hand to the organization to help flood-affected people.

Figure 3. Emergency relief for the flood-affected people (A: Emergency relief, B: Emergency relief, C: Relief packaging team, D: Packaged emergency relief)

Figure 4. Emergency relief distribution, rescue operation and activities in medical camps (A: Rescue operation, B: Gatherings in medical camps, C: Medicine in medical camps, D: Books and other emergency relief in medical camps)

Figure 5. Activities in medical camps (A: Registration, B: Medicine for flood-affected people, C: Treatment provision by doctors, D: Treatment provision by doctors, E: Books distribution among the children, F: Free medicine provision for the flood-affected people after treatment)

List of medicine: Analgesic (Paracetamol, Ketorolac tromethamine), Antibiotic (Levofloxacin, Metronidazole, Amoxicillin, Bacitracin and Neomycin combination), Antihistaminic (Desloratadine), Antifungal (Econazole nitrate 1% and Triamdnolone combination), Antiscabies (Permethrin 5%), Anti-allergic (Chlorpheniramine maleate), Antacids (Famotidine: Histamine H2 Blocker), Bronchodilators (Levosalbutamol, Ketotifen), and Nasal decongestant (Sodium Chloride 0.9%)

3.3. Phase II: Post-flood recovery and community health response

Post-flood activities primarily focused on rehabilitating families displaced due to partial or complete damage to their homes. In Chagalnaiya, Feni district, approximately 35 families received financial assistance from Nogorful and other associated organizations to repair and reconstruct their houses.

A significant initiative during the recovery phase was the staging of medical camps, led by Nogorful’s Health and Nutrition team in collaboration with other voluntary organizations. Venues were selected in collaboration with local and district authorities and various other voluntary organizations. On the day before the camps in Feni and Noakhali, on 6 and 28 September, respectively, a team of volunteers made public announcements via megaphone to inform local flood-affected people.

Each camp began with patient registration and basic health screening, which included noting the patient’s complaints, measuring body temperature, blood pressure, body weight, and respiratory rate. Following this, the attending doctors conducted clinical assessments and provided symptomatic treatment based on presumptive diagnoses. A wide range of essential medicines was distributed free of charge, including antibiotics for respiratory and gastrointestinal infections, analgesics, antihistamines, antifungals, antiscabies medications, anti-allergics, antacids, bronchodilators, and nasal decongestants. Patients with wounds also received wound care, dressing, and suturing. The complex cases mean that patients with symptoms across more than one physiological system were given a single broad-spectrum antibiotic. Administration of antibiotics is sensitive due to the consequences of antimicrobial resistance. Patients with miscellaneous diseases were provided with vitamin supplements and referred to specialized consultants, as most were over 61 years of age.

In addition to medical treatment, beneficiaries received cooked meals, clothing, hygiene kits, educational and religious books, and stationery for students. In total, nearly 1,000 individuals, including women and children, received medical services and relief in two medical camps. A 40-member volunteer team comprising doctors, nurses, pharmacists, and logistical staff supported the initiative.

3.4. Demographic distribution of beneficiaries (N=682) of the medical camps in September 2024

Figure 6 shows that 54.3% of illnesses were among community members from Feni, whereas 45.7% were among those from Noakhali. Of the affected individuals, 36.4% were male, and 63.6% were female. Most were adults aged >25 to 61 years (43.6%), followed by children aged 1 to 13 years (24.9%), youth aged >13 to 25 years (21.3%), older adults aged >61 years or older (7.3%), and infants aged <1 year (2.9%).

Figure 6. Demographic distribution of the beneficiaries (N=682) of the medical camp during the August 2024 Flood.

3.5. Distribution of reported illnesses by physiological systems and complexity (multi-systems involvement) among beneficiaries (N= 682) of the medical camps, September 2024

Most individuals (46.5%) sought treatment for integumentary diseases, followed by respiratory diseases (13.2%) and miscellaneous diseases (11%) (Figure 7). They presented with single (58.5%) and multiple (41.5%) symptoms, while individuals with integumentary and respiratory diseases were more complex (100%), often accompanied by respiratory diseases and other miscellaneous conditions (Figure 8). Particular individuals with respiratory diseases also showed more than 2 respiratory tract symptoms (54.4%). The beneficiaries with miscellaneous diseases were recorded with multiple symptoms (38.3%) (Figure 8).

Figure 7: Distribution of the reported illnesses by physiological system among the beneficiaries (N=682) of the medical camps in September 2024 [Miscellaneous= Cardiac, metabolic, malnutrition, nervous system, in this group these systems were present singly or combinedly; Other systems also denoted these miscellaneous groups singly or combinedly]

Figure 8: Distribution of the recorded symptoms (single and multiple) of the reported illness and complexity of the illness based on involvement with multiple physiological systems of the beneficiaries (N=682) of the medical camps in September 2024

3.6. Distribution of reported illnesses associated with different physiological systems by the demographics of beneficiaries (N= 682) of the medical camps after the August flood 2024 through univariate analysis

Table 2 shows that the prevalence of diseases of the integumentary system was higher in the presented cases in Noakhali (54.5%, $p < 0.001$) than in Feni (39.5%). However, the prevalence of cases associated with the skeletal system (6.5%), the gastrointestinal system (4.6%), and the combined respiratory and other systems (4.1%) was significantly higher in Feni than in Noakhali. Almost half of the male cases (52%) showed a significantly higher prevalence of integumentary cases than female cases (43.1%). Integumentary cases were most prevalent in children (1-13 years) (54.7%), followed by young (13-25 years) (51.7%) and infants (below 1 year) (45%). The cases of miscellaneous systems

were most commonly reported in older adults (above 61 years) (40%), followed by infants (below 1 year) (15%), and adults (25-61 years) (10.4%).

Table 2. Distribution of reported illnesses of different physiological systems by the demographic characteristics (Location/Gender/Age) of beneficiaries (N= 682) of the medical camps, September 2024

Demographic characters		Physiological systems							
Variables	Categories	Integumentary system, %	Respiratory system, %	Miscellaneous systems, %	Integumentary and miscellaneous systems, %	Integumentary and respiratory systems, %	Skeletal system, %	Gastrointestinal system, %	Respiratory and other systems, %
		Location	Feni	39.5	14.6	12.7	8.7	9.3	6.5
	Noakhali	54.5	11.5	9.	11.9	9.5	3.2	0.6	0
p-value (x ² test)		<0.001	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.9	0.05	0.002	<0.001
Gender	Male	52	10.5	10.9	9.7	7.3	4.8	3.6	1.2
	Female	43.1	14.8	11.1	10.4	10.6	5.1	2.3	2.8
p-value (x ² test)		0.02	0.1	0.9	0.8	0.1	0.9	0.3	0.2
Age (years)	Below 1	45	25	15	0	5	0	5	5
	1-13	54.7	11.2	6.5	10	8.2	4.1	2.4	2.9
	Above 13 to 25	51.7	11.7	6.9	10.3	8.3	4.1	4.1	2.8
	Above 25 to 61	42.8	14.8	10.4	10.8	11.5	5.7	2.7	1.4
	Above 61	24	10	40	10	6	8	0	2
p-value (x ² test)		0.001	0.3	<0.001	0.7	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.7

Post-hoc residual analysis confirmed these trends, showing significant overrepresentation of integumentary diseases in Noakhali and underrepresentation in Feni (standardized residual = ±3.92, adjusted p-value = 0.0014). Likewise, older adults were significantly more likely to report miscellaneous conditions and less likely to present with integumentary illnesses (standardized residual = +6.81; adjusted p-value <0.001). A heatmap visualizing these associations is provided in Figure 9, and detailed post-hoc results are available in Table 3.

Figure 9: A heat map of standardized residuals from chi-square post hoc analysis showing the relationship between demographic groups and physiological system involvement. [Standardized residuals > |2| indicate significant deviation from expected frequency]

Table 3. Post Hoc analysis table through residuals standardization and adjusted p-values of significant association between demographic categories and reported illness (N=682) of different physiological systems.

No.	Category	System	Residual	p_adj	Significant	Variable
1	Feni	Integumentary	-3.92084215	1.411841e-03	Yes	Location
2	Noakhali	Integumentary	3.92084215	1.411841e-03	Yes	Location
13	Feni	Gastrointestinal	3.12554747	2.839591e-02	Yes	Location
14	Noakhali	Gastrointestinal	-3.12554747	2.839591e-02	Yes	Location
15	Feni	Resp_Other	3.59626209	5.165161e-03	Yes	Location
16	Noakhali	Resp_Other	-3.59626209	5.165161e-03	Yes	Location
37	Above 61	Integumentary	-3.28996666	4.007970e-02	Yes	Age
47	Above 61	Miscellaneous	6.80957426	3.915535e-10	Yes	Age

3.7. Multinomial logistic regression model of demographic characteristics (Location/ Gender/ Age) for human illness (N=682) of different physiological systems reported in the medical camps after the August flood 2024 [Reference: Integumentary System]

To adjust for potential confounders, a multinomial logistic regression model was constructed using demographic characteristics (location, gender, and age group) to predict illness types. The model explained approximately 5.3% of the variance in illness types, indicating limited explanatory power and suggesting that demographic factors alone do not adequately explain the distribution of illness in flood-affected populations, and that broader environmental exposure and contextual factors likely play an important role. Significant findings included a lower relative risk of presenting with respiratory, miscellaneous, skeletal, and gastrointestinal illnesses (RRR range = 0.05-0.57; 95% CI: 0.007-0.928; $p < 0.05$). Additionally, beneficiaries aged above 61 years had a significantly higher relative risk of presenting with miscellaneous system illnesses (RRR = 6.10, 95% CI: 1.35–27.71, $p = 0.019$). Full model coefficients and confidence intervals are available in Table 4.

Table 4. Multinomial logistic regression of demographic characteristics (Location/ Gender/ Age) for human illness (N=682) of different physiological systems reported in the Nogorful-led medical camps after the August flood 2024 [Reference: Integumentary System]

Sub-categories	Outcome	Risk ratio	p-value	95% confidence interval
Noakhali	Integumentary system	0.57	0.024	0.007–0.7
Male		0.60	0.05	0.04-0.928
Noakhali	Miscellaneous	0.50	0.01	0.132–0.245
Above 61		6.12	0.02	0.299-0.532
Noakhali	Skeletal system	0.05	0.004	0.15–0.95

3.8. Volunteers' perception regarding the organization's growth, operational learning, and community resilience

3.8.1. Organizational transformation through crisis response

Nogorful has achieved significant transformation following its active leadership in supporting flood-affected people during the August 2024 flood, according to the volunteers' statements. The organization earned noticeable public interest, volunteer engagements, and donor response, paving the way for developing a more coordinated emergency response system, partnerships among the stakeholders, and establishing a rapid mobilization protocol.

“After the flood, Nogorful became more structured and united. Serving over 500 people was no easy task, but strong leadership and seamless teamwork made it possible. I am proud to be part of this team.” –Volunteer of Nogorful, medical student.

“Social media and local news portal engagement spiked after the flood activity, and many new volunteers (Nogor Mali) and medical professionals reached out expressing interest in joining. Local donors also showed more trust, and there was an uptick in community donations and support. People began recognizing the organization for its wider humanitarian value.” –Volunteer of Nogorful, research fellow of the World Health Organization.

The activities carried out during the flood enhanced the organization’s capacity (such as early reporting and documentation) and the individual capabilities (such as leadership, communication, responsibility, and risk-taking) of its members, as mentioned by the volunteers of Nogorful.

“The flood response taught us the power of quick coordination, calm leadership, and decentralized teamwork. We learned to plan for uncertainty, rely on clear communication, and lead with compassion. From mobile medical kits to field documentation, every lesson has made us stronger and more prepared.” –Volunteer of Nogorful, research fellow of the World Health Organization.

“I was appointed as the leader of the clothing distribution during that time and learned many things, like willingness to achieve the target, teamwork, humanity, and risk-taking.” –Volunteer of Nogorful, college student.

Participants consistently described appreciation as a vital source of motivation for their voluntary engagement. Many highlighted how the compassionate efforts of Nogorful’s members during the flood response were recognized and praised by community members, which in turn reinforced their sense of purpose and commitment.

“Nogorful’s dedication was recognized widely — from community elders and local leaders to national media, their response efforts earned heartfelt praise and public appreciation.” –Vice President of Nogorful, Society for Health Extension and Development, World Food Programme.

“We did everything only from Humanity, not for recognition, but some media, international organizations, and local leaders also worked with us. The most important recognition for a volunteer is prayer, and we got affected people’s gratitude, Alhamdulillah!” –Volunteer, student of master’s course.

4. Discussion

This study presents a novel mixed-methods approach to evaluating the dual role of a non-profit voluntary organization (NVO) in both managing public health risks and institutional growth during the August 2024 flood in Bangladesh. By integrating epidemiological data with qualitative insights, the study demonstrates how grassroots organizations can complement formal disaster governance, respond to urgent community needs, and simultaneously build internal resilience and societal legitimacy, as discussed in the following sections.

4.1. Role of NVOs in complementing formal disaster governance

The Ministry of Disaster Management and Relief (MDMR) leads Bangladesh’s disaster response, defining the roles of government and non-government agencies (NGOs) and civil society across all administrative tiers (Ahmed et al., 2017; Hossain, 2020). It oversees disease management across the four disaster phases: risk reduction, warning, emergency response, and recovery (Ahmed et al., 2017). In contrast, NVOs voluntarily join disaster coordination teams and collaborate with NGOs during large-scale emergencies (Hossain, 2012). Their activities are more flexible and less constrained by bureaucracy (ISDR, 2006; Hossain, 2012), focusing mainly on emergency and post-disaster relief, medical support, rescue, and rehabilitation, while risk-reduction planning remains the primary responsibility of government entities (Ahmed et al., 2017; Cvetković & Radonjić, 2020).

Flood disasters affect the broader safety and stability of local communities, reinforcing the importance of coordinated preparedness and response systems, as observed in flood-risk studies conducted in Belgrade and other urban settings (Cvetkovic & Martinović, 2020). In this study, a volunteer-led organization (NVO) contributed to emergency and post-disaster support by mobilizing funds, conducting rescue operations, distributing relief, and providing medical aid. However, its reach remained under 1% of the affected population due to resource constraints (Ahmed et al., 2017). It also collaborated with other NVOs in the Chattogram region, forming part of a broader grassroots response—similar to how community-based organizations in Nepal, the Philippines, and Japan have filled critical gaps in disaster governance by supporting rapid response, shelter management, and community resilience when government capacity was overstretched (Shaw & Goda, 2004; Gaillard and Texier, 2010; UNDRR, 2019). Such evidence highlights that, despite limitations in scale, grassroots initiatives can substantially complement formal disaster management frameworks. However, in Bangladesh, governance still prioritizes emergency and recovery phases over risk reduction, and weak institutional integration often prevents accurate loss assessment, undermining budget allocation for both immediate and long-term needs (Sabur, 2012; Ahmed et al., 2017; Al-Hasan et al., 2024; Cvetković, 2024). In this context, the close community engagement of NVOs represents an underutilized asset for strengthening field-level assessments and enhancing the effectiveness of national disaster management frameworks.

4.2. Public health implications

Flood-related health diseases observed in this study underscore persistent challenges in post-disaster medical response. Skin and respiratory conditions were the most prevalent, consistent with flood literature, in which prolonged water exposure, overcrowding, malnutrition, and poor sanitation drive integumentary, respiratory, and malnutrition-related illnesses (Acosta-España et al., 2024; UN, 2024). The higher proportion of female beneficiaries (63.6%) aligns with socio-cultural health-seeking behaviors in Bangladesh, where women are often more accustomed to seeking community-based medical support (Cvetković et al., 2018; Uddin, 2025). Statistical analyses revealed significant variation in illness distribution across age, gender, and location, yet the regression models explained only a small proportion of the variance. This indicates that illness patterns are also strongly influenced by environmental factors (flooding severity with consequences), and contextual factors (social cohesion, community support network, government and NVOs coordination, disaster risk policies, response capacity to medical services and access to clinics, income, transport access and supply of relief materials) (Alderman et al., 2012; Saulnier et al., 2017; UNDRR, 2022). Immediately after flooding, transport networks, healthcare facilities, and emergency response systems are often severely disrupted, limiting affected populations' ability to access essential services promptly (Perić, J. and Cvetković, V.M., 2019). In addition, weak coordination between government agencies and local non-profit volunteer organisations can delay the mobilization of response activities, further constraining early relief and medical support (WHO, 2026a; WHO, 2026b). Delayed response (10–30 days post-flood) and reliance on self-reported symptoms likely contributed to underestimation of acute conditions (Graves, 2013; Calderaro et al., 2022). Strengthening NVO-government integration could improve timely and effective medical response, data collection, and targeting of vulnerable populations, thereby enhancing post-flood public health outcomes. A formal memorandum of understanding (MOU) between the government and NVOs can strengthen the operational framework during emergencies by defining roles, responsibilities, and coordination protocols.

4.3. Organizational transformation and community resilience

Participation in flood response catalyzed significant organizational development within Ngorful. Volunteers gained leadership, teamwork, logistical planning, and rapid decision-making skills, improving the organization's ability to act swiftly in future crises. Recognition by local communities and media reinforced intrinsic motivation, improved volunteer retention, and strengthened trust in the organization. These findings resonate with disaster literature, which shows that crises often

serve as turning points for local NVOs, strengthening operational capacity, volunteer morale, and societal legitimacy (Twigg, 2009; Deverell, 2013; Whittaker et al., 2015; Nolte & Martin, 2021). Beyond organizational benefits, this adaptive learning process also contributes to broader community resilience: grassroots actors embed practical skills, knowledge, and social capital at the local level, reducing dependence on external aid and enabling communities to better prepare for and withstand future shocks. Thus, Nogorful's experience illustrates how even small-scale, resource-limited NVOs can evolve into more resilient and trusted institutions through crisis engagement, simultaneously building internal robustness and external societal value.

Strengthened collaboration between government agencies and non-profit volunteer organisations can further enhance these gains by institutionalising coordinated response mechanisms. This integrated disaster management unit can be employed to address training and accountability. Joint training and simulation exercises can improve interoperability, align operational procedures, and enhance the safe and effective delivery of volunteer services. Designating government liaison officers within integrated emergency response structures can facilitate continuous communication, rapid coordination, and clearer role definition for volunteer groups. Standardised documentation and reporting systems, covering service delivery, patient encounters, and resource requirements, can further improve accountability, situational awareness, and evidence-based decision-making. Such structured collaboration not only enhances response efficiency but also supports the professional development of volunteers, expands youth engagement in humanitarian action, and strengthens long-term community resilience.

5. Conclusion and recommendation

This study examined the typical functions and capacity-building potential of a non-profit voluntary organization (NVO) in Bangladesh using a mixed-methods approach during a flood disaster. By supplementing qualitative insights with Quantitative analysis of epidemiological patterns of post-flood human illnesses, the significant role played by a student-led NVO in emergency response. Although the single-case design and reliance on self-reported experiences limit the generalizability of the findings, the methodological rigor and triangulated evidence provide transferable lessons for similar disaster-prone contexts.

To enhance national disaster preparedness, the study recommends formal recognition and integration of emerging NVOs into disaster coordination mechanisms. The study identifies a scope for outbreak surveillance following natural disasters to estimate public health hazards in collaboration between NVOs and government organizations. Strengthening institutional linkages, providing technical and financial support, and initiating joint training programs between government bodies and NVOs could improve data collection, expedite emergency response, and promote community resilience. In disaster-prone countries like Bangladesh, unlocking the full potential of local volunteer organizations can bridge institutional gaps and support inclusive disaster governance.

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